

Comparing Free Reference Extraction Pipelines

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Abstract

Purpose: In this paper, we compare the performance of several popular pre-trained reference extraction and segmentation toolkits combined in different pipeline configurations on three different datasets. **Methods:** The extraction is end-to-end, i.e. the input is PDF documents, and the output is parsed reference objects. The evaluation is for reference strings and individual fields in the reference objects using alignment by identical fields and close-to-identical values. **Results:** Our results show that Grobid and AnyStyle perform best of all compared tools, although one may want to use them in combination. **Conclusion:** Our work is meant to serve as a reference for researchers interested in applying out-of-the-box reference extraction and -parsing tools, for example, as a preprocessing step to a more complex research question. Our detailed results on different datasets with results for individual parsed fields will allow them to focus on aspects that are particularly important to them.

Keywords: reference extraction, reference segmentation, toolchain, parsing, scholarly document processing

1 Introduction

Citations are one of the most prominent features of scientific literature. They implement the very core of the scientific process, i.e., the idea of standing on the shoulders of giants by crediting and referencing previous work. Although this may not have been entirely obvious from the start, scientific references are not only interesting to the reader of the publication that contains them. Any scientific publication is usually designed to maximize its utility for future work, often approximated as the number of references it receives from other publications. As the future references are not known at the time of the publication of the referenced work, it is not possible to record the publications that cite a certain work (i.e. the forward look on the *citing* works) within this work

– although this may be equally as relevant as the conventional backwards looking record on the *cited* works. In addition to the number or the exact list of citing documents given a specific work, the entire network of referenced documents or a particular strain may interest people ignorant of the content of the individual publications therein. Such researchers may be referred to as *bibliometricians* or *scientometricians*.

As the first of their kind, *Eugene Garfield* is generally credited with having founded the discipline of recording and studying scientific citation networks after being inspired by *Shepard's Citations*, a similar solution for American court cases [66]. Starting with his *Science Citation Index* [17] citations or references have been extracted from the publications they appear in and collected in external resources ever since. This was initially

conducted manually and is still done in this way, although the effort has probably been moved to the authors of publications as they are asked to provide a list of references when publishing their work. In addition, the vast growth in the volume of new scientific literature [36] makes it attractive to automatically extract this information when manually curated references are unavailable. This is supported by the fact that many citation indices continue to be proprietary, largely overlapping [52], and expensive to use [29]. Instead, automatic extraction offers the option to obtain a set of references given the publication in electronic text (like UTF, ASCII), structured form (like DOC, XML, HTML), or print medium (like PDF, PS).

Many tools have been proposed for automatic reference extraction from scientific publications. Some tools may only be able to process certain input types (well). In addition, many different ways of presenting scientific work in general and referenced work in particular exist. Venues have different page formatting and reference styles, including footnote referencing. Considerable high-level differences in conventions of different kinds may exist between different scientific domains. Some tools may be more suitable for some of them.

In this work, we offer decision support for choosing reference extraction tools. We conduct an empirical evaluation of different toolchains applied to PDF publications, mainly from the social and geosciences. These publications have been manually processed to extract and parse their references, which allows for reliable evaluation of the performance of the compared tools. We distinguish the task of extracting simply the reference string from its subsequent parsing into a reference object, i.e., a set of meta-information on the referenced publication. In contrast to other comparisons, our contributions are focused on:

1. ... observing toolchains, i.e. combinations of tools, not just individual ones
2. ... evaluating based on individual reference object fields
3. ... using an advanced mapping procedure to match extracted and gold fields

In the following, we discuss related work in Section 2 and the compared tools in Section 3, describe our experimental setup in Section 4 and the corresponding results in Section 5 before we conclude in Section 6.

2 Related Work

We briefly summarize the research on reference extraction and parsing. The tools that we have been able to identify as being presented in the literature are listed in Table 1 along with their name, the year of the publication, whether they extract or parse references, and how they do so.

2.1 Reference extraction

Reference extraction and parsing is a special case of information extraction. Classical information extraction (including all reference extraction methods listed in this paper) use traditional techniques like multivariate classifiers (e.g. *Support Vector Machines (SVMs)* [65] or sequence labelling (e.g. *Conditional Random Fields (CRFs)* [35], or *Hidden Markov Models (HMMs)* [18], or *Structured SVMs* [60]) to produce a sequence of labels for a given input text sequence. Likewise, a multipurpose generative model will produce a natural language text sequence for an input sequence. Given recent breakthroughs in generative AI using *Large Language Models (LLMs)*, various groups have experimented with re-purposing LLMs for information extraction. [1, 3, 5, 37, 51, 62, 64, 70] In the most popular instance of such generative models, namely a chat bot, the input sequence is considered a question or instruction and the output a natural language answer. When using a chat bot like ChatGPT for information extraction, the input needs to contain both the instruction (e.g. ‘extract all references’) and the text to extract from (e.g. a part of a publications full-text) and the output needs to be turned into a machine-readable, standardized format. Given the unnecessary overhead of turning a formalized problem such as reference extraction into a natural language query and then again interpreting a natural language output, it is more efficient to consider which aspect the LLM is really contributing compared to traditional approaches, and isolating those, while still using the fast and predictable traditional methods for labelling. [25] For example, the LLM’s vast background knowledge may include aspects of reference matching, correction and completion out-of-the-box (cf. [14, 63]).¹

¹Yann LeCun’s post on LinkedIn may also be of interest: <https://tinyurl.com/w4yk5nmm> [accessed 3rd March 2024].

One way of combining an LLM’s natural language capacities and background knowledge with a dedicated labelling method is to (fine-)tune an auto-regressive model specifically to take text sequence as input and output only the desired formal output. [31] Another way is using an LLM’s ability to creatively produce varied correct natural language texts (with annotation) to produce training samples (e.g. texts with made-up annotated references or parsed references) in a much cheaper way than using human annotators. This allows to create very large and variable silver-standards that can in turn be used to train task-specific compact classical models. [19, 55, 61] At this point, we have not been able to identify scientific works that use LLM’s to obtain reference extraction or parsing tools. We have experimented with using Llama2 prompts to extract references, but we have noticed issues with hallucination as well the high cost of having to enter the entire full-text with chopped substrings as individual prompts. There are plenty of scientific works introducing reference extraction and parsing methods. We have collected all the works that we could find in Table 1. Some only extract reference strings, some only parse reference strings, and some do both. Some of these have become known under a specific name, such as *ParsCit*, *Grobid* or *Cermin*. For most of the scientifically described methods, tools or working code cannot be (readily) retrieved, and many have never been given a name under which they may be found. Many methods are very old. Some published tools are described in the literature, while others are not. Of the fewer methods available as tools, many are not maintained anymore. In the following section, previous comparisons of tools are discussed. Those studies evaluated some of the listed tools as poorly performing.

2.2 Tool comparison

We have identified seven publications concerning the comparison of reference extraction software. Lipinski et al. [38] compare the tools *Doccar’s PDF Inspector*, *Grobid*, *Mendeley Desktop*, *ParsCit*, *PDFMeat*, *PDFSSA4MET*, *SciPlore Xtract*, *SVMHeaderParse* and *Zotero* for the task of extracting bibliographic metadata. Although many of the tools also extract references, this is not the focus of their comparison. Instead, they

are looking at metadata features of the publication (not of its references), i.e. title, authors, abstract and publication year. Here Grobid stands out with the best performance, but Mendeley Desktop and SVMHeaderParse also show acceptable performance. Körner et al. [34] compare tools specifically for reference extraction, however, look only at the reference string extracted, not its parsed version. Their tool RefExt outperforms all other tools², but Grobid follows in second place and Cermin as well as ParsCit also offer acceptable results. Complementing this research, Tkaczyk et al. [57] compare tools for the next step, namely the parsing of reference strings into nested reference objects that contain the metadata (like title, publication year and author names) provided for these publications in the references themselves. They list *AnyStyle*, *Biblio*, *BibPro*, *Cermin*, *Citation*, *Citation-Parser*, *Free_cite*, *Grobid*, *Neural ParsCit*, *ParsCit*, *PDFSSA4MET*, *Reference Tagger* and *Science Parse* and evaluate all of them except BibPro, Free_cite and Neural ParsCit, which they could not get to run. The results show an outperforming Grobid, followed by Cermin and then ParsCit. Mediocre performance is reported for AnyStyle³, Reference Tagger and Science Parse. Biblio, Citation, Citation-parser and PDFSSA4MET show poor performance. In a similar study, two additional aspects were studied in the same year. (A) Tkaczyk et al. [59] present a recommender for citation parsers, which presents a ranking of parsers for a given reference string such that the likelihood of a better-performing parser being ranked before another is maximized. Picking the top-recommended parser for any given reference string is shown to improve parsing performance compared to the single best-performing parser (Grobid). Apparently, some parsers work better for specific references than others, and these types of references can be detected to some degree by the used features (reference string length, number of commas, number of parentheses, etc.). Notably, they do not study the option to run all parsers on all reference strings and then combine their results optimally. (B) Tkaczyk et al. [58] compare the performance gains achieved over

²We have not been able to reproduce this.

³In our experiments, AnyStyle was a strong parser, so, likely, there have since been considerable improvements.

the pre-trained models when retraining a reference parser on gold data closer to the test data. While Grobid is already very strong in its pre-trained version and only gains 3 percentage points, ParsCit and Cermine gain considerably by retraining them. In particular, Cermine reaches the same F1 as a retrained Grobid. Probably, their models are very similar (both are CRFs), and the data used to train them is the main difference between their pre-trained versions.

Indrawati et al. [30] also compare Grobid, Cermine and ParsCit, specifically to the case of Indonesian Scientific Journals. The results suggest that Grobid and Cermine perform best, closely followed by ParsCit. Recently, Cioffi and Peroni [7] have compared end-to-end tools that do both reference string extraction and subsequent reference string parsing. They compare AnyStyle (preceded

Table 1: Reference extraction and parsing tools that are described in scientific literature or are available as tools. Issues: *availability*—no code found; *running*—problems running code; *installation*—problems installing; *quality*—poor results reported; *legacy*—officially abandoned; *proprietary*—not free-to-use.

publication	name	year	type	technique	code	issues
Constantin et al. [9]	PDFX	2013	extract	style-analysis	?	availability
Cuong et al. [13]		2015	extract	CRF	?	availability
Kern et al. [32]	TeamBeam	2012	extract	style-analysis	?	availability
Körner et al. [34]	RefExt	2017	extract	CRF	java	✓
Peng and McCallum [46]		2006	extract	CRF	?	availability
Councill et al. [12]	ParsCit	2008	extract+parse	regex+CRF	perl	running
Guo and Jin [23]		2011	extract+parse	KB	?	availability
Gupta et al. [24]		2009	extract+parse	regex+KB	?	availability
Lopez [39]	Grobid	2009	extract+parse	CRF	java	✓
Tkaczyk et al. [56]	Cermine	2014	extract+parse	CRF	java	✓
Zou et al. [71]		2010	extract+parse	CRF+SVM	?	availability
Chen et al. [6]	BibPro	2010	parse	sequence alignment	java	installation
Cortez et al. [10]	FLUX-CIM	2007	parse	KB	?	availability
Cortez et al. [11]		2009	parse	KB	?	availability
Day et al. [16]		2007	parse	KB	?	availability
Hetzner [26]		2008	parse	HMM	python	availability
Hsieh et al. [28]		2014	parse	sequence alignment	?	availability
Kim et al. [33]	BILBO	2012	parse	CRF	?	availability
Namikoshi et al. [40]		2017	parse	CRF	?	availability
Ohta et al. [41]		2012	parse	CRF	?	availability
Ohta et al. [42]		2014	parse	CRF	?	availability
Ojokoh et al. [43]		2011	parse	HMM	?	availability
Staelin et al. [53]	Biblio	2007	extract	SVM+NN	perl	quality
Prasad et al. [48]	Neural ParsCit	2018	parse	NN	python	running
Suryawati and Widyantoro [54]		2017	parse	regex+rules+classif.	?	availability
Yin et al. [67]		2004	parse	bigram HMM	?	availability
Zhang et al. [68]		2011	parse	CRF	?	availability
Zhang et al. [69]		2011	parse	SVM	?	availability
Groza et al. [22]		2012	segment+parse	CRF	?	availability
pypi → citation-parser	citation-parser	2019	parse	?	python	running
AnyStyle.io	AnyStyle	2024	parse	CRF	ruby	✓
code4lib → FreeCite	FreeCite	2009	parse	?	ruby	installation
github → reftagger	RefTagger	2015	parse	?	python	legacy
github → pdfssa4met	pdfssa4met	2013	extract+parse	?	python	quality
github → science-parse	SPv1	2019	extract+parse	?	java	legacy
github → spv2	SPv2	2018	extract+parse	?	python	legacy
scholarcy.com	Scholarcy	2024	extract+parse	?	API	proprietary

by *pdftotext*), *Cermine*, *EXparser*, *Grobid*, *PDFSSA4MET*, *Scholarcy* and *Science Parse* and distinguish three task levels: (a) extract the set of reference strings, (b) determine the set of labels that the parser needs to assign to parts of a given reference string and (c) determine the set of part-label pairs for this reference string. We also use their gold standard in our evaluation. Similar to our experience and different from Tkaczyk et al. [57], *AnyStyle* performs well in their evaluation. The best full results are obtained by *AnyStyle*, *Grobid* and *Cermine*. *AnyStyle* (slightly) outperforms in each individual task. *EXparser* only works well in the second task. Interestingly, *AnyStyle* dominates the extraction task, although it cannot use visual layout information when simply using the text input from *pdftotext*. *PDFSSA4MET* continues to strongly underperform in this comparison. *Science Parse* shows mediocre performance compared to which the proprietary *Scholarcy* is better, but not as good as the top three ‘usual suspects’ *AnyStyle*, *Grobid* and *Cermine*.

Over all comparisons done over the years, the outstanding tools seem to be *Grobid*, *Cermine*, *AnyStyle* and (Neural) *ParsCit*. Soft weight-based or probabilistic models such as conditional random fields or neural networks outperform rule- or regex-based approaches, especially for reference string extraction.

2.3 Datasets and (re-)training

For training, tuning and testing end-to-end reference extraction and parsing, two types of datasets are required: (a) those that align input documents (e.g. in PDF format) with the reference strings that can be found in them; (b) those that align reference strings with parsed reference objects. The assumption is that the aligned outputs constitute the correct target for training, testing and tuning. The systems must, therefore, produce outputs of the same format, such that the deviation between the system output and the gold standard can be compared in terms of the system’s performance. The closer the system output is to the gold output, the better its performance. A system is considered better than another if it performs better on such datasets. Large datasets of the above kind benefit both the quality of the systems by offering more training examples and the significance of their comparison, so several efforts have been made to

create them. Colavizza and Romanello [8] have annotated references in fulltext documents about the history of Venice. Their annotation includes manually parsed reference objects and identifying the reference strings. They have used it to train CRF reference parsers and extractors. Grennan et al. [21] have created a large set of references in different reference styles by implementing a reference generator that takes publication metadata as input and outputs the respective reference strings for different reference styles. This does not seem to include any alignment between documents and the references mentioned therein and is hence of limited use to the extraction task.⁴ It is mainly advertised for training reference string parsers. In a related publication, Grennan and Beel [20] explore the use of this dataset for re-training *Grobid* and comparing the performance of the re-trained model against its out-of-the-box counterpart. Unsurprisingly, the results are that each model performs best on the data it was trained on and that for each dataset, the model that was trained on it performs best. For a third dataset, both models performed equally well. The training data used as an alternative to the original *Grobid* data was an equally large subset of the synthetic dataset mentioned above. Larger subsets did not consistently improve the results a lot. This should question, to some extent, the usefulness of very large datasets. Peroni and Shotton [47] have created and are maintaining *OpenCitations*, which is a large database that lists reference objects for many publications Daquino et al. [15]. It is our impression that the reference lists are not necessarily complete. Therefore, using this dataset to assess the precision of extraction tools should be difficult. The datasets used by us for evaluation are *GEOcite* by Birkeneder et al. [2], *ExCite* by Hosseini et al. [27] and *CIOFFI* by Cioffi and Peroni [7]. The latter is not freely available due to some PDFs not being open-access. However, it has been appended with a new open-source section by Pagnotta [44] for future use.

⁴It should be noted that a simple collection of reference strings or reference objects without the alignment to the original input document can also be used to train an extractor. This is because the collection can be used to learn a model of how references look like in contrast to normal text. Then, any input document can be scanned for substrings that match the learned patterns exceptionally well. However, this does not allow for tuning and evaluation.

3 Compared tools

We need to limit our selection as we are comparing not simply different tools but different combinations thereof. We do not compare tools or methods that are officially abandoned, that cannot be easily installed or run (e.g. requiring python2), that are behind a paywall, that do not have a machine interface or that have already been ruled out as poorly performing in previous comparisons. These issues are also listed in Table 1. Therefore, we only compare Grobid, AnyStyle, Cermin and ExParser. These have different input and output options, as listed in Table 2, which allows for different pipeline arrangements. We also include *pdftotext*, which returns the text from a given PDF for completeness. For example, AnyStyle can search for references in fulltext extracted by *pdftotext*. Generating all possible combinations, we end up with one pipeline for each path in Figure 1.

3.1 EXparser

EXparser [4], developed in the scope of the EXCITE project [27], is a tool based on machine learning. Its distinctive feature is that it aims to handle high-variance references. High-variance means references of a wide range of formats and locations, e.g., the tool can handle references in footnotes. EXparser relies on manually extracted textual and layout features for extraction and segmentation. Random Forest is used as a classifier for extraction, and Conditional Random Fields are used for segmentation. The final step in the process is checking the completeness of a reference, which is estimated by probability density functions on segmented reference strings.

3.2 Grobid

Grobid [39] is arguably the most popular tool for end-to-end reference extraction and parsing. It is

still maintained and can extract parsed references when given a PDF file⁵. The results consistently rank among the best when compared to other tools. References are only one type of information that it extracts. It also finds images, paragraphs, titles, authors and many other features, creating a completely structured representation of the publication. It can also be used to extract fulltext from a PDF, although this information is spread across many different fields. Finally, it also returns the reference strings in unparsed form.

3.3 Cermin

Cermin [56] is similar to Grobid. The difference seems to be slightly worse performance in its pre-trained form (c.f. Tkaczyk et al. [58]), slower speed and different input and output options. Cermin can also simply parse given reference strings and provides layout files for a given PDF.

3.4 AnyStyle

AnyStyle is, first and foremost, a parser for reference strings, but it can also discover them in surrounding fulltext. It cannot directly work with PDFs, which requires *pdftotext* or another fulltext extraction tool to be run first. Its performance is quite good and seems to have been improving recently (cf. Tkaczyk et al. [57] vs Cioffi and Peroni [7]), making it a relatively new alternative to Cermin and Grobid.

4 Experiments

We evaluate all toolchains against three gold standards as described in the following section. We separate the performance by the following fields that any reference parser will commonly identify: reference string, title, publication year, author names, editor names, publisher, source (e.g. journal or collection), volume and issue (if journal article), start-page and end-page (in the source). Reporting results separately for different fields allows the reader to identify which tools perform best for the fields most important to the user. Performance on the reference string as such evaluates extraction without parsing. Extraction of global identifiers like URL, DOI, or arxiv-id

Table 2: Input and output options of the tools.

INPUT				TOOL	OUTPUT				
•			◦ ⁵	Grobid	•	•	•	•	•
•			•	Cermin	•	•	•	•	•
	•	•	•	AnyStyle			•	•	
				ExParser					•
•				pdftotext		•			
pdf	layout	text	refstr		layout	text	refstr	refobj	meta

⁵According to [58], Grobid can be used to parse reference strings, but we did not see how as noted for Grobid in Table 2.

Fig. 1: The toolchains evaluated as best performing in green, and the noncompetitive ones greyed out.

would be desirable, but the different tools handle these differently: AnyStyle extracts DOIs, Grobid extracts arxiv-ids, and neither Cerminor Exparser extracts any of them. However, in our framework, we have verified that it is easy to use regular expressions and URL resolution to extract such identifiers from the reference string in a post-processing step.

4.1 Datasets

We use three datasets of manually extracted and parsed references that have been created in the EXCITE⁶ project [27], in the GEOCITE⁷ project [2], and by Cioffi and Peroni [7], respectively⁸. The assumption is that the tools that best approximate the gold standards are the best-performing tools. The EXCITE dataset contains 348 full-text PDFs with metadata from the SSOAR⁹ repository. The GEOCITE dataset contains 178 full-text PDFs from the geosciences domain. Both contain German and English documents and scans that require OCR. The CIOFFI dataset is described in Cioffi and Peroni [7] and contains 56 relatively

recent English scientific papers sampled from various domains. Table 3 presents some statistics about the number of annotated references.

4.2 Evaluation measures

To evaluate different extraction and parsing tools, we compare the parsed reference objects against the reference objects as provided in the gold standard. This means we compare two nested objects. Requiring the parsers to reproduce exactly the gold reference object would make the task too difficult. Allowing irrelevant minor differences, we want the parsers to approximate the gold object as much as possible. If a parser approximates a gold object to some extent, this should also count towards its performance score. The attribute-value matching done for evaluation is illustrated in Figure 2. As a first simplification, we assume that both gold and parsed reference objects are sets of attribute-value pairs. This ignores nestedness (for example, it does not matter if a surname belongs to the first or second author) and order (e.g. of authors). So it will suffice if all the surnames are found, all the first names are found, etc. We consider it unlikely that a tool systematically swaps name parts between different authors or changes the order of authors mentioned, so these relaxed requirements should not unjustly favour some tools over others, in contrast to overly restrictive requirements that can indeed arbitrarily favour certain tools based on irrelevant minor differences.¹⁰ Further, we assume that the values in these attribute-value pairs need not match exactly but only closely (for example, additional whitespace or capitalization should be ignored).

⁶<https://github.com/exciteproject>

⁷<https://github.com/GeoCite>

⁸As the gold standard by Cioffi and Peroni [7] does not include the extracted, unparsed refstrings, we had to create artificial ones from the provided parsed refobjects, assuming that these will be sufficiently similar to the original refstrings.

⁹www.ssoar.info

Table 3: Number of references per document in the EXCITE, GEOCITE and CIOFFI datasets.

	# Docs	# Refs	Mean	Lowest	Highest	0-19	20-39	40-59	60-79	80-99	100-119	120-139	140-159
GEOCITE	178	4729	27	0	109	86	48	29	7	5	3	0	0
EXCITE	348	8679	25	1	151	162	111	63	8	2	0	1	1
CIOFFI	56	2536	45	10	113	5	23	14	9	4	1	0	0

¹⁰Consider the case of the BLEU score [45] in machine translation, which under normal assumptions will measure translation quality well, although it is possible to intentionally produce a bad translation with a good score.

reference	Abeshouse, Bob, The Koch Brothers -People & Power: Al Jazeera English. N.p., 1 Nov., 2011. http://www.aljazeera.com/programmes/peopleandpower/2011/10/2011102683719370179 .html [Accessed on 16 Nov. 2011.]														
	[1] Abeshouse, Bob, The Koch Brothers - People & Power: Al Jazeera English. N.p., 1 Nov., 2011. http://www.aljazeera.com/programmes/peopleandpower/2011/10/2011102683719370179 .html [Accessed on 16 Nov. 2011.]														
	2011	Al Jazeera English. N.p	author	Bob	Abeshouse	The	Koch	Brothers	People	Power	title				
2011			Bob	Abeshouse						The Koch Brothers - People & Power: Al Jazeera English					
reference	Vgl. Engel, Ulf (2005) : Deutschland, Afrika und die Entstehung gemeinsamer Interessen, in: Aus Politik														
	Engel, Ulf (2005): Deutschland, Afrika und die Entstehung gemeinsamer Interessen, in: Aus Politik und Zeitgeschichte 4/2005, 11–17.														
	2005		author	Ulf	Engel	Vgl	Aus Politik	in	title	: Deutschland, Afrika und die Entstehung gemeinsamer Interessen	volume	4	start	11	end
2005	Aus Politik und Zeitgeschichte		Ulf	Engel					Deutschland, Afrika und die Entstehung gemeinsamer Interessen						

Fig. 2: Two visualized examples of matchings between aligned system (blue, Positive) and gold (yellow, True) references. Green indicates a match (True-Positive). We count the coloured boxes towards TP, P and T to compute precision as $\frac{TP}{P} = \frac{4}{10}$ (top) or $\frac{TP}{P} = \frac{5}{8}$ (bottom) and recall as $\frac{TP}{T} = \frac{4}{5}$ (top) or $\frac{TP}{T} = \frac{5}{6}$ (bottom). Note that in our evaluation, we count TP, T and P over all references of a given document and separate the counts by fields (for example, ‘author’). The final results are the average over the individual documents’ precision and recall.

Consider that we are evaluating a parsing problem, which is mostly about sequence labelling. Mistakes in one part of the parsing will affect other parts. This means that it is unlikely that the accepted differences will grant an unfair advantage to some tools, as even an accepted mistake will correspond to further unaccepted mistakes in other parts. We require that a maximally different parse has a very low score, a perfect parse has a perfect score, and anything in between gives a reasonable fine-grained impression of how correct the parse is. The more wrong a parse is, the worse should be the score. If a is more wrong than b , then the score of a should be lower than that of b . We argue this is achieved as follows: After the attribute-value pairs are obtained, they are grouped by attributes. Then, for each attribute, the optimal pairing between gold and reference values is computed based on a string similarity measure (in our case, the Python *difflib Sequence-Matcher* based on the algorithm by Ratcliff et al. [50] for strings and Boolean equality for other values like numbers) and the *linear sum assignment* or *minimum weight matching*. This *unbalanced assignment problem* [49] is a fairly expensive combinatorial optimization, but since the compared sets of values for a given attribute are quite small, it is feasible in practice. We assume that alignment

of two values for the same attribute is necessary but not sufficient for them to match. If not sufficiently similar, values may still be aligned by the above algorithm for lack of better alternatives. After the above described alignment, a threshold on the Ratcliff et al. [50] alignment similarity or possibly any other string similarity measure is applied to determine whether the aligned values are sufficiently similar to be considered a match. In our matching, the alignment similarity was divided by the number of characters of the shorter aligned value in case of most string attributes and a threshold was roughly tuned manually by inspection in a reference-to-metadata-collection matching scenario on different data.¹¹ For year attributes, we allow a maximal integer difference of 1 between the values.¹² For all other attributes, we require exact value match. Trues (T) is the number of elements in the gold-standard object. Positives (P) is the number of elements in the extracted object. And true-positives (TP) is the number of matching element-pairs. Then precision and recall are computed as TP/P and TP/T ,

¹¹We consider it unlikely that this threshold’s fine-tuning favours some tools over others.

¹²While this matters in other matching applications, here it essentially amounts to exact match of extracted and true year.

EXCITE, where AnyStyle applied on pdftotext fulltext has the most (8/11 incl. *refstr*) top-F1 columns. However, for those fields where AnyStyle on pdftotext performs better than AnyStyle on Grobid-extracted reference strings, the latter is only slightly worse (1-3%). On CIOFFI, again AnyStyle on Grobid performs best, with 7/11 incl. *refstr*. This shows that AnyStyle is clearly useful, whether applied on Grobid-extracted reference strings or on pdftotext fulltext. Tools other than AnyStyle or Grobid are not competitive according to our comparison (see also Figure 1). Cermin performs worst, while ExParser, which uses Cermin-extracted layouts but not Cermin-extracted reference strings, performs better for some features – and worse for others. Cermin seems not to parse editors and publishers. The performance of most tools’ reference extraction is similar to the performance of their parsing, except for ExParser, which has particularly poor performance here. On the contrary, the worst part of

Cermin is its parser (compare AnyStyle references from Cermin reference strings to Cermin end-to-end). However, AnyStyle also works better with the basic pdftotext fulltext input than with Cermin or Grobid full-text input. Overall, the best choice is to use AnyStyle parser and Grobid-extracted references.

5.2 Comparing our Evaluation

Comparing our results on the CIOFFI dataset against those on GEOCITE and EXCITE, as well as on those reported in Cioffi and Peroni [7], we note that our CIOFFI evaluation is very similar to our GEOCITE evaluation – except for *AnyStyle references from Cermin fulltext* vs. *AnyStyle references from Cermin references* regarding reference string and year. The original results reported by Cioffi and Peroni [7] are different, in particular the poor performance of Grobid reference extraction surprises, given that Grobid provides some of

Table 5: Percentage-drop (magenta; not %-point-drop!) from best performance (violet) in Table 4. For example, *refstr*-F1 is 4% lower than the best result (87) for *cermin refs*→*anystyle* on GEOCITE.

% drop	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R	P F1 R
GEOCITE	refstr	title	year	author	editor	publ	source	vol	issue	startp	endp	
cerm.txt-anyst	95 11 21	3 16 25	1 13 20	8 17 25	18 30 33	15 24 33	4 14 22	10 13 17	12 18 23	12 19 23	9 17 22	
cerm.ref-anyst	5 4 7	4 9 12	3 4 6	9 10 13	17 17 17	7 16 22	6 11 16	8 7 6	12 15 20	9 10 11	3 8 12	
grob.txt-anyst	1 1 3	89 2 3	94 2 6	7 5 4	57 2 2	26 4 7	1 1 1	5 4 3	8 6 9	2 1 2	84 1 2	
grob.ref-anyst	5 87 83	89 83 78	2 84 78	5 2 1	1 46 39	26 25 27	72 69 67	78 66 57	47 44 43	2 78 76	84 79 75	
pdftotxt-anyst	95 6 13	2 10 16	3 8 14	9 13 17	15 15 15	7 16 18	2 8 13	7 10 12	47 4 11	9 12 15	8 12 17	
cermin	5 4 7	10 18 23	4 7 11	21 24 27	– – –	– – –	34 46 52	26 24 20	38 50 55	30 33 35	13 25 34	
grob.ref-cermin	5 87 83	89 4 7	3 2 3	2 19 33	– – –	– – –	27 34 38	25 19 13	34 38 39	25 26 26	9 18 25	
cerm.layo-exp	7 14 21	5 15 21	9 17 25	16 24 32	22 26 28	38 56 59	19 24 28	30 24 20	14 15 16	29 33 36	28 35 40	
grobid	5 87 83	3 6 8	5 2 78	71 75 81	18 43 53	3 28 37	6 18 26	6 1 57	21 34 44	82 78 2	1 1 1	
EXCITE	refstr	title	year	author	editor	publ	source	vol	issue	startp	endp	
cerm.txt-anyst	93 2 10	90 3 9	93 2 8	82 2 9	67 5 5	52 1 7	72 2 8	73 3 8	46 44 2	77 5 13	80 9 14	
cerm.ref-anyst	4 5 12	5 7 10	3 5 9	4 6 10	10 11 13	9 11 16	1 2 7	5 4 8	8 13 17	2 5 10	1 6 9	
grob.txt-anyst	6 3 5	7 5 6	4 3 4	8 4 4	2 1 53	5 3 5	9 4 1	1 1 6	4 2 4	1 1 2	80 77 1	
grob.ref-anyst	10 2 87	9 3 82	5 1 83	8 2 84	5 3 53	5 51 53	8 2 69	2 64 3	2 44 45	2 75 1	1 77 75	
pdftotxt-anyst	3 87 2	2 84 1	3 86 1	3 81 1	67 59 53	3 51 53	1 69 69	4 1 3	6 2 2	77 75 2	80 2 4	
cermin	4 5 12	9 15 23	4 6 12	19 24 32	– – –	– – –	26 33 40	16 14 16	21 29 37	18 19 24	3 18 26	
grob.ref-cermin	10 2 87	11 8 9	5 2 2	15 28 40	– – –	– – –	30 33 37	20 12 8	15 18 24	15 16 18	6 12 18	
cerm.layo-exp	6 9 17	5 8 13	6 12 20	9 17 26	11 6 53	3 13 24	9 10 14	21 12 6	6 4 6	23 25 28	23 25 29	
grobid	10 2 87	14 8 7	9 3 1	9 3 84	23 44 52	9 19 30	20 26 31	6 1 60	15 27 37	3 1 75	6 5 2	
CIOFFI	refstr	title	year	author	editor	publ	source	vol	issue	startp	endp	
cerm.txt-anyst	3 10 17	4 13 19	2 10 18	17 14 19	42 37 22	15 8 3	10 16 20	5 14 20	– – –	6 17 27	6 16 24	
cerm.ref-anyst	94 3 5	2 5 8	92 3 7	14 6 6	36 29 8	17 8 3	13 11 10	2 5 10	– – –	3 8 13	7 9 12	
grob.txt-anyst	1 2 2	1 2 3	1 2 4	12 2 3	19 4 2	63 56 54	2 1 3	1 2 3	– – –	2 6 9	89 2 4	
grob.ref-anyst	1 93 93	1 92 92	92 92 92	10 1 1	19 24 36	9 7 3	1 86 91	90 90 91	– – –	2 5 7	89 87 2	
pdftotxt-anyst	3 8 12	7 11 16	4 10 16	21 15 17	52 50 22	14 8 1	10 15 18	7 12 16	– – –	6 16 22	7 14 19	
cermin	94 3 5	3 9 16	92 4 8	16 10 14	– – –	– – –	18 18 20	3 6 8	– – –	2 6 9	4 6 11	
grob.ref-cermin	1 93 93	93 1 2	1 1 2	74 10 28	– – –	– – –	4 4 6	1 1 1	– – –	1 4 7	1 87 1	
cerm.layo-exp	2 10 17	5 11 18	8 20 29	24 22 29	68 83 61	34 36 40	12 16 20	27 30 32	– – –	14 21 27	21 24 27	
grobid	1 93 93	2 1 1	92 92 92	9 77 92	15 41 52	9 10 11	83 1 3	90 1 2	– – –	90 91 92	2 87 87	

Fig. 3: One toolchain with two extracted, parsed and linked references in the OUTCITE demonstrator.

the best reference extraction in our experiments. Their results align better with our overall results for parsing (metadata and content) evaluation, although they do not provide results for individual fields. In general, from their description, it seems that their evaluation is based more on identifying expected spans in the provided text compared to extracting substrings mostly identical to the expected values as in our case, which explains the result divergence (for example, some tools extract a reference number before the reference, while others do not, which could be considered a mistake in their evaluation, but not in ours).

6 Conclusion

We have conducted an empirical evaluation of different toolchains applied to PDF publications from the social sciences (EXCITE), geosciences (GEOCITE) and a broader mix of domains (CIOFFI). These publications had been manually processed (not by us) to extract and parse their references, which allows for reliable evaluation of the compared tools' performance. We have distinguished the task of extracting only the reference string and parsing a reference string into a reference object, i.e., a set of meta-information on the referenced publication. When comparing several existing tools in different combinations, we find that a subset consisting of pdftotext, Grobid and AnyStyle is relevant. We expect that when tweaking the full-text-extraction from Grobid-extracted XML, one can do better than pdftotext, leaving just Grobid and AnyStyle. One should also note that Cermin is quite slow compared to Grobid. Our comparison enables users interested in particular fields to make their own choices based on the individual performance reported for those. Based

on our evaluation, we recommend using AnyStyle for parsing and Grobid for extraction.

Resources

For testing the toolchains evaluated in this paper, we provide a demo system at <https://demo-outcite.gesis.org/> which shows the reference extraction and parsing results of uploaded PDF files (see Figure 3). Further, we provide the code for our framework at <https://github.com/OUTCITE/outcite-refextract> or <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/directory/b8b3db04fb8212d3b5cda0f45a2e86bc57833257/> and under *doi*: 10.5281/zenodo.10985784, which includes the evaluation script as well as the gold data. The authors are willing to help interested readers navigate our repositories and apply our framework to their systems to foster dissemination, exploitation and reproducibility.

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